

acephate treatments. The differences in results from the cited paddy-water study and from the contact toxicity study reported here may be due to different modes of action of the insecticide in the two application methods. Insecticides applied in the paddy water may have acted primarily as a stomach poison, but the insecticides in this study acted as contact poisons, entering through the cuticle rather than the mouthparts. At any rate, knowing that BPH biotypes differ in their susceptibility to insecticides is important and should be considered when developing strategies for BPH control. *W*

Contact toxicity of insecticides applied with Potter's spray tower at 0.04% concentration against three brown planthopper biotypes. IRRI greenhouse, 1977.

Insecticide	Formulation	Mortality ^a (%)		
		Biotype 1	Biotype 2	Biotype 3
Decamethrin	2.5 EC	93 a	97 a	90 a
Carbofuran	2 F	68 b	98 a	97 a
Metalkamate	30 EC	64 b	99 a	97 a
Acephate	75 SP	37 a	47 a	37 a
Diazinon	20 EC	24 b	49 a	43 a
Methyl parathion	50 EC	11 b	47 a	35 a
Control		6 a	6 a	4 a

^aMortality reading taken 48 hours after treatment. Average of 4 replications, each consisting of 25 adult insects. Any means for each biotype followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Resistance of brown planthopper to various insecticides at IRRI

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In 1977 carbofuran failed to control the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* at IRRI. Studies using Potter's spray tower and paddy water broadcast methods of application indicated that the strain of BPH that had been exposed to carbofuran for several years (field strain) was resistant (see article, this issue). Further studies using the microapplicator were conducted to compare the field strain's level of resistance to carbofuran and to other insecticides with that of a greenhouse strain that had not been exposed to insecticides.

Both sexes of the field strain had seven times more resistance to carbofuran than the greenhouse strain (see table). The field strain had two to five times

The LD₅₀ value of insecticides applied topically to greenhouse and field strains^a of female and male brown planthoppers. IRRI laboratory, 1977.

Insecticide	Female		ERR ^b	Male		ERR ^b
	LD ₅₀ (µg/g)			LD ₅₀ (dg)		
	Greenhouse strain	Field strain		Greenhouse strain	Field strain	
Carbofuran	0.14	1.05	7.50	0.25	1.78	7.12
Monocrotophos	0.65	3.50	5.38	0.49	2.00	4.08
Metalkamate	1.46	5.37	3.67	2.00	8.68	4.34
Methyl parathion	7.67	23.19	3.02	10.52	13.90	1.32
BPMC	1.95	5.29	2.71	2.89	11.80	4.08
MIPC	1.42	3.29	2.30	5.23	5.59	1.06
Endosulfan	3.09	5.94	1.92	5.12	12.46	2.43
Acephate	2.93	4.96	1.69	3.56	7.79	2.18
N 3727	28.90	32.43	1.12	41.46	43.41	1.04
Perthane	5.13	5.70	1.11	4.45	10.46	2.35
A47171	4.07	4.07	1.00	6.66	5.81	0.87

^aThe greenhouse strain had not been exposed to insecticide and was reared in the greenhouse for about 30 generations. The field strain was reared in the greenhouse for about 4 generations.

^bEstimated resistance ratio = LD₅₀ of field strain divided by LD₅₀ of greenhouse strain.

more resistance to other insecticides that had been used to varying extents at the IRRI farm. Monocrotophos and MIPC have been most commonly used for about

5 years. There was no resistance to newly developed coded compounds, such as N 3727 and A 47171, that had never been used on the farm. *W*

Heavy brown planthopper reinfestations nullify effectiveness of insecticides

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Insecticidal control has often been insufficiently effective against the brown planthopper (BPH) during massive outbreaks over extensive areas. Rapid

and heavy reinfestations from unaffected BPH populations probably are a significant reason, particularly where the entire affected area cannot be treated effectively, uniformly, and simultaneously, as is common under normal field conditions. This was especially evident in recent insecticide trials in Sekinchan, Malaysia, during a BPH outbreak on the rice variety MR 7 at 20 to 26 days after transplanting.

Two fields of 2 ha each were treated with 2 kg a.i. carbofuran/ha (granular broadcast) and 0.1% a.i. monocrotophos (foliar), respectively. Immediately after treatment, 10 plants spaced over each field were randomly selected; each plant was individually enclosed with cylindrical wire and nylon screen cages. The BPH populations on these plants were determined just before treatment and periodically afterwards. Similar BPH

counts were made on 26 uncaged plants randomly selected in each field.

Except on the uncaged plants treated with carbofuran, the BPH populations on all plants examined were drastically reduced soon after treatment (see figure). That confirms earlier glasshouse findings that both chemicals were highly effective. Monocrotophos acted very rapidly, causing 100% BPH mortality 6 hours after treatment. But 3.6 BPH/hill were still alive on carbofuran-treated plants at 1 day after broadcasting. On plants of both cage treatments, however,

1st-instar nymphs emerged 2 days after treatment, suggesting that BPH eggs were already present and were not affected. Macropterous adults soon reappeared on exposed monocrotophos-treated plants and, like those on exposed carbofuran-treated plants, rapidly increased. The buildups were undoubtedly due to immigrants, as the populations consisted largely of macropterous adults from nearby fields of mature plants. Under such a situation, the fresh BPH influx not only nullifies the potential effectiveness of the applied insecticides but also leads to serious hopperburn (see table).

The findings revealed that 1) heavy immigration of BPH can render potentially effective chemicals ineffective, and 2) hopperburn will ensue when the reinfestation rate exceeds the rate of insecticidal kill, leaving a BPH population

Effectiveness of carbofuran and monocrotophos in the control of the brown planthoppers under outbreak condition in Sekinchan, Malaysia.

Plant conditions in a 2-ha rice field (variety MR 7) treated with 2 kg a.i. carbofuran/ha during a brown planthopper outbreak in Sekinchan, Malaysia, 1977.

Date	Plants (%)			
	Green	Slight yellowing	Intense yellowing	Hopperburn
<i>July 1977</i>				
20 ^a	100	0	—	—
21	95	5	—	—
22	95	5	—	—
23	90	10	—	—
26	75	25	—	—
28	70	30	—	—
29	60	40	—	—
30	40	30	30	—
<i>August 1977</i>				
1	15	40	40	5

^aBroadcast of carbofuran granules.

that exceeds the economic injury level. Those factors probably contribute to or account for the numerous unsuccessful

attempts to control large-scale BPH outbreaks by chemicals in many countries. ❧

Spray volumes in relation to brown planthopper control

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The Philippine recommendations for brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* control in rice state that 333, 500, and 1,000 liters water/ha are required to spray crops at 15, 35, and 60 days after transplanting (DT), respectively. It is extremely difficult for the applicator to carry this much water over 1 ha of lowland rice. An IRRI Cropping Systems Program survey indicated that most farmers apply only about 135 liters/ha.

Studies were conducted in 1977 to

determine the relationship between volume of spray solution applied and BPH control. Perthane was applied at 60 DT. The percentage of BPH control was equal for all volumes from 200 to

1,000 liters/ha (see table). Results in a repeated experiment were similar. Further studies with other insecticides will be conducted before current recommendations are reevaluated.

Effect of spray volumes on the control of the brown planthopper (BPH) on variety IR22. IRR1, 1977 wet season^a

Treatment 0.75 kg a.i. Perthane/ha at indicated volumes (liters)	Concn (%)	BPH ^b (no./hill)		Control (%)
		Before spraying	4 days after spraying	
200	0.38	911 a	112 a	88
400	0.19	750 a	98 a	87
600	0.13	867 a	66 a	92
800	0.09	673 a	52 a	92
1,000	0.08	820 a	80 a	90
Control (300 liters water)	0.00	908 a	694 b	24

^aTo induce buildup of BPH population, the field was sprayed six times with 25 g a.i. cypermethrin/ha at 10-day intervals.

^bIn a column, any means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.